

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

Articles for publication in the International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) should observe the following guidelines and style.

Guidelines

- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) may accompany each article. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Contributions should be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses should be done.
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Pest survey data should be quantified. Give infection percentage, degree of severity, etc.

Style

- For measurements, use the International System. Avoid national units of measure (cavan, rai, etc.).
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha, 2 h/d.
- Express yield data in tonnes per hectare (t/ha). With small-scale studies, use grams per pot (g/pot) or g/row.
- Express time, money, and common measures in number, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 min. \$2, 3 kg/ha, 2-wk intervals.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or higher numbers. For example: six parts, seven tractors, four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 in Thailand, and 12 in Indonesia.
- Write out numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were put in each cage. Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer.
- Place the name or denotation of chemicals or other measured materials near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha, not 60 kg/ha N; 200 kg seed/ha, not 200 kg/ha seed.
- Use common names — not trade names — for chemicals.
- The US\$ is the standard monetary unit in the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- When using acronyms, spell each out at first mention and put the specific acronym in parentheses. After that, use the acronym throughout the paper. For example: The brown planthopper (BPH) is a well-known insect pest of rice. Three BPH biotypes have been observed in Asia.
- Abbreviate names of months to three letters: Jun, Apr, Sep.
- Define in the footnote or legend any nonstandard abbreviations or symbols used in a table or figure.
- Do not cite references or include a bibliography.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization OVERALL PROGRESS

IRRI varieties and advanced lines used in China

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From 1971 to 1982, 3,335 varieties and advanced lines were introduced in China from IRRI. Some are highly resistant to blast (BI) and bacterial leaf blight (BB), and have good plant type with high yield potential. Those varied lines are grown by farmers and used for rice improvement programs in China. They are IR8, IR24, IR661 selection, IR26, IR28, IR29, IR30, IR36, IR1529-680-3, IR2061-464-2-4-5,

Yuan-Feng-Zao is a new variety developed by irradiating IR8 seeds with 35,000 r units of Co⁶⁰ gamma rays. Yuan-Feng-Zao is a first-season indica with 107-110 d duration. It is suitable for large areas along the Yangtze River. It is grown on about 1,200,000 ha.

Hybrid rice is planted on about 5.3 million ha in China. Most hybrids are indicas and involved IRRI varieties as restorer lines (Table 2).

The best hybrid combinations involve the Shan-you system, especially Shan-you 6, which has resistance or tolerance to BB and tolerance to brown planthopper, and stable yield. Its restorer line is IR26. Shan-you 6 is grown as a single crop or second-season rice on about half of the hybrid rice areas along the Yangtze River. □

Table 1. Summary of data on 5 superior varieties grown in China.

Variety	Release year	Planted area (ha)	Yield potential (t/ha)	Main advantage	Main growing area
IR8	1968	913,000	7.5 to 9.0	High yielding	South, Central, and Southwest China
IR24	1973	433,000	7.50	Good plant type	Central and South China
IR661 selection	1973	62,000	7.50	Good plant type	Central and part of South China
IR26	1975	70,700	6.0 to 7.5	Highly resistant to both BI and BB	Central China
Xiao-jia-huo (IR1529-680-3)	1975	63,000	6.0 to 7.5	Highly resistant to BI and BB	South China

IR2061-465-1-5-5, and IR1561-228-3-3. The most widely used varieties are IR8, IR24, IR661 sel., IR26, and IR1529-680-3 (Table 1).

Many IRRI varieties have been used in rice improvement programs for conventional breeding, radiation breeding, and hybrid rice development.

Xiang-Ai-Zao is from IRg/Xiang-Ai-Zho 4. It is an early-season indica bred by the Rice Research Institute (RRI) of Hunan Academy of Agricultural Sciences (HAAS), and grown on more than 65,000 ha in 1978. Many new indica semidwarfs have been developed from IR8 parentage.

Table 2. Major combinations of indica hybrid rice grown in China.

Hybrid rice	Combination
Shan-you 2	Zhen-shan 97A/IR24
Shan-you 3	Zhen-shan 97A/IR661 Sel.
Shan-you 6	Zhen-shan 97A/IR26
Wei-you 2	V20A/IR24
Wei-you 3	V20A/IR661 Sel.
Wei-you 6	V20A/IR26
Si-you 2	V41A/IR24
Si-you 3	V41A/IR661 Sel.
Si-you 6	V41A/IR26
Nan-you 2	Er-Jiu-Nan 1A/IR24
Nan-you 3	Er-Jiu-Nan 1A/IR661 Sel
Nan-you 6	Er-Jiu-Nan 1A/IR26